

NOTATKA / NOTE

A new record of *Parnopes grandior* (Pallas, 1771) (Hymenoptera: Chrysididae) from the Masovian Lowland (Central Poland)

Nowe stanowisko sawczyнки piaskowej *Parnopes grandior* (Pallas, 1771) na Nizinie Mazowieckiej

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ABSTRACT. The paper presents a new locality of the rare cuckoo wasp *Parnopes grandior* (PALLAS, 1771) in Poland. A total of eight observations (four of solitary females, three of solitary males, and one of two interacting males, representing at least three distinct individuals) were made in June 2024 in Sewerynów (Masovian Lowland; UTM ED50). The species was recorded in the habitat of its host, *Bembix rostrata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). The site is characterized by high biodiversity and a rich community of psammophilous arthropods. According to available data, *P. grandior* has not been previously recorded in this area.

KEY WORDS: cuckoo wasps, psammophilous arthropods, *Bembix rostrata*.

Parnopes grandior (PALLAS, 1771) is a rare cuckoo wasp, classified as Critically Endangered (CR) in Poland (BANASZAK 2002). It is a brood nest parasitoid of sand wasps (POLIDORI et al. 2020), in Poland primarily *Bembix rostrata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). After over 50 years without records, contemporary sites were recently discovered in eastern and north-eastern Poland (JAROSZEWICZ 2007, WIŚNIEWSKI 2015). This note presents a new locality from the Masovian Lowland – an analysis of the historical and contemporary distribution (JAROSZEWICZ 2007, TWERD & BANASZAK 2018, SZYMKIEWICZ & SZYMKIEWICZ 2021, SACHANOWICZ & ŻURAWLEW 2022) indicates that there were no previous records of *P. grandior* in the discussed region of the Masovian Lowland (UTM ED50).

Observations were made in Sewerynów near Korytnica (Masovian Lowland; UTM ED50). The site covers an area of approximately 0.5 ha, encompassing a sandy dirt road and a mosaic of sandy wasteland (class III/IV soil) and ruderal vegetation. Observations were conducted on June 18–20, 2024, between 10:15 and 16:15, under warm, and mostly sunny conditions, with temperatures ranging from 20°C to 30°C.

A total of eight observations (four of solitary females, three of solitary males, and one interaction of two males, representing at least three distinct individuals) were recorded: 18 VI 2024: 1♂ on a sandy

dirt road, 2♂ interacting (mistaken mating attempt or territorial fight) on a sandy dirt road, 1♀ on a sandy dirt road near *Bembix rostrata* nests (GBIF occurrence: 4901153978), 1♂ on the flowers of *Jasione montana* L. (GBIF occurrence: 4901222288); 19 VI 2024: 1♀ on a sandy dirt road near *B. rostrata* nests (GBIF occurrence: 4901115953), 1♀ on a sandy dirt road near *B. rostrata* nests, 1♀ on the flowers of *J. montana*; 20 VI 2024: 1♂ on an old wooden pallet in a home garden. All specimens were observed, photographed, and identified by W. Siekierzyński. The sex of the observed individuals was verified from photographs by B. WIŚNIEWSKI. Photographic documentation was taken under natural conditions (Fig. 1, Fig. 2, Fig. 3).

The host population of *B. rostrata* has been observed annually at this site for several years, with its size estimated at several to a dozen individuals, depending on the year. In addition to the host, the site is inhabited by many other specialized psammophilous taxa. Among the most interesting accompanying species are the rare bee *Dasygoda morawitzi* RADCHENKO, 2016 (observed in 2023), the cuckoo wasp *Hedychrum chalybaeum* DAHLBOM, 1854 (recorded in 2022, 2023, and 2025), as well as representatives of crabronid wasps: *Tachytes panzeri* (DUFOUR, 1841) (2024), *Dinetus pictus* (FABRICIUS, 1793) (2025) and *Bembecinus tridens* (FABRICIUS, 1781) (2024, 2025).

Fig. 1. Female of *Parnopes grandior* (Sewerynów, 18 VI 2024; photo by W. SIEKIERZYŃSKI).

Fig. 2. Male of *Parnopes grandior* resting on an old wooden pallet in a home garden (Sewerynów, 20 VI 2024; photo by W. SIEKIERZYŃSKI).

Fig. 3. Interacting males of *Parnopes grandior* (Sewerynów, 18 VI 2024; photo by W. SIEKIERZYŃSKI).

Fig. 4. Location of *Parnopes grandior* in Sewerynów, Map generated using the MapaUTM program (GIERLASIŃSKI 2026).

The presence of the methochid wasp *Methocha articulata* (LATREILLE, 1792) (2025) was also recorded here. The presence of a stable host population and such a rich faunal background, highlights the ecological importance of this anthropogenic habitat patch for the survival of *P. grandior*.

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